

The G.R.E.A.T Concept: Building a Good Governance Culture in the Malaysian Public Sector

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Abstract

Globalisation and the swift advancement of technology have made it challenging for public sectors all over the world to provide their services. In order to meet the needs of its citizens, this has put tremendous pressure on the public sectors to work more and provide better services. Malaysia, though, has not fallen behind. However, a lot of positive action has been taken to address such challenges. Therefore, this paper discusses the rise of the G.R.E.A.T. concept that has been introduced to Malaysian Public Sector as a tactical tool to implement the finest services. Institutionalising the G.R.E.A.T. (Good Governance, Responsible, Empathy, Accountability, Tenacity of Purpose) concept in the public sector is a fundamental premise of stepping up to success in government according to MADANI aspiration. G.R.E.A.T is a value-laden principle that encourages ideal institutional conformance in the conduct of public affairs. In summary, the critical discussion presented in this paper will serve to develop Malaysian Public Sector activities while also serving as a reference for best practices for other ASEAN countries. The review's conclusions shed some light on the doable outcomes for governments' success.

Keywords: *Good Governance, Responsible, Empathy, Accountability, Tenacity of Purpose, Malaysia MADANI.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Malaysian Public Sector plays a crucial role in driving economic growth, providing social services, and ensuring the well-being of its citizens. It encompasses a wide range of ministries, departments, agencies, and statutory bodies, each with distinct responsibilities and contributions to the nation's development. The Malaysian Public Sector is structured in a hierarchical manner, with three main levels, the first being the federal government which is the highest level responsible for national policies, programs, and institutions. The second level is the state government that oversees matters within their respective states, aligned with federal guidelines and finally the third level encompassing the local authority that manages local affairs such as sanitation, infrastructure, and community development, within their jurisdictions.

One of the key challenges of the Malaysian Public Sector is striking a balance between managing budget deficits and optimizing resource allocation while ensuring the continued delivery of high-quality public services [1]. Additionally, the public sector must adapt to the evolving dynamics of an aging population and increasing urbanization, ensuring

that its services cater to the diverse needs of all citizens. Embracing new technologies can enhance service delivery, improve efficiency, and foster innovation [1]. However, it is crucial to manage these advancements effectively to avoid disruptions and ensure equitable access to technological benefits. Public expectations also play a significant role in shaping the public sector's agenda. Rising expectations for efficient, transparent, and citizen-centric services demand a continuous commitment to improvement and innovation. Recognizing these challenges and embracing the opportunities presented by evolving trends, the Malaysian Public Sector is committed to continuous improvement and strives to become a world-class organization that delivers excellence in service delivery, promotes economic prosperity, and ensures the well-being of all Malaysians [1].

As Malaysia strives to realize its vision of a developed and dynamic country, the Malaysian Public Sector plays a crucial role in strengthening its capabilities, competence, and professionalism. This unwavering commitment to excellence is essential to navigate the challenges and seize the opportunities that lie ahead on the path to national prosperity. To achieve strong and flexible policies, leaders must thus share the specially designed public sector governance centered with public servants. It will be necessary to tailor governance practices to the specific needs and characteristics of public sector organizations. Thus, the G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service initiative's founding is consistent with the significance it places on bolstering its public sector governance. Therefore, the objective of this conceptual paper is twofold:(i) to introduce specially designed public sector governance initiative, G.R.E.A.T. and (ii) to discuss the impact and execution of the initiative on service delivery.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Good Governance

The concept of governance has been around for many years and derives from the Greek verb *kubernaein* [*kubernáo*] which means to steer [2]. The definition of governance would depend on its intended purpose depends on the people involved, and the socio-political environment of the term [3]. The World Bank defines governance as the way power is exercised to regulate the economic and social resources of a country for development [4]. Similarly, The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) defines governance as the exercise of economic, political & administrative authority to manage a country's affairs at all levels [5]. The definition by United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (UNESCAP) denotes governance as the process of decision-making and process by which decisions are implemented (or not implemented) [6].

Good governance addresses the allocation and management of resources to respond to collective problems. World Bank in its report year 1994, discourses the characteristics of good governance as predictable, open, and enlightened policymaking (that is, transparent processes); add a bureaucracy imbued with a professional ethos and a strong civil society participating in public affairs and all behaving under the rule of law [7]. Good governance is measured by eight major elements namely participatory, consensus oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive, effective, and efficient, equitable and inclusive and follows the rule of law [6]. Good governance practices would encourage better service delivery and

accountability by establishing a benchmark for aspects of good governance in the public sector [8].

2.2 Malaysia MADANI

The term Malaysia MADANI is a policy framework and government slogan that was introduced by YAB Dato' Seri Anwar Ibrahim, the 10th Prime Minister of Malaysia which encompasses Sustainability, Care and Compassion, Respect, Innovation, Prosperity and Trust [9]. These are the six Malaysian values based on the Prime Minister's vision for a stronger, better Malaysia. The framework provides a method of developing policies after surviving the pandemic and restricting the country. It prioritises good governance, sustainable development, and racial harmony as its core objectives [10]. The policy framework underscores the government's commitment to a synthesis approach, seamlessly integrating established practices with innovative methods to effectively address emerging challenges and uncertainties.

2.3 The G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service

The **G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service** initiative is the brainchild of the Chief Secretary to the Government of Malaysia, YBhg. Tan Sri Dato' Seri Mohd Zuki bin Ali that is more towards supporting the values of Malaysia MADANI. This initiative aims to empower civil servants with superior personal values, fostering a more effective and ethical public service [11]. The G.R.E.A.T. acronym embodies the core values of Good Governance, Responsible, Empathy, Accountable, and Tenacity of Purpose. These values serve as the anchor of the Malaysian Public Sector, guiding and inspiring its members to uphold the highest standards of integrity, professionalism, and service excellence. This initiative is a pivotal endeavour aimed at elevating the performance and reputation of the Malaysian Public Sector. By placing a strong emphasis on personal values, the initiative aims to cultivate a culture of excellence within the public sector, one that is unwaveringly committed to serving the people of Malaysia with dedication, integrity, and empathy.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF MALAYSIAN PUBLIC SECTOR GOVERNANCE

Good governance, Malaysia MADANI, and G.R.E.A.T are not solo concepts but rather interconnected pillars that support the nation's development. In the pursuit of a sustained and balanced nation, the Malaysian Public Sector has embarked on a journey guided by these principles. Aiming to create a prosperous Malaysia through its public sector, Figure 1 presents the interconnected and interdependent concepts that form a synergistic framework. It then translates these principles into tangible actions, ensuring that the government keeps its promises to the people which inextricably linked to the principles of good governance and the aspirations of Malaysia MADANI.

Figure 1: Driving Force Model of Malaysian Public Sector

3.1 Good Governance: The Foundation

Figure 1 shows the Malaysian Public Sector as a building, with good governance as the foundation in which it is essential for the effective and efficient operation of any organisation, including the public sector. Good governance is the bedrock of a prosperous nation, ensuring a robust and effective public sector. It is a thorough framework that includes eight key tenets that guarantee the government functions in the best interests of all citizens, cultivate public trust, and empower people to actively engage in decision-making. It ensures that public access to government operations and public accountability for government actions are maintained.

A government that adheres to these principles is more likely to build trust, address citizens' needs promptly, and create a fair and effective system that promotes overall societal well-being. This trust is essential for effective collaboration, enabling the government to harness the collective wisdom and energy of its people, including those involved in the public sector, to achieve shared goals. It empowers citizens to become active participants in shaping their nation's future, ensuring that their voices are not merely heard but also heeded. When the public sector is well-governed, it can lead to a number of positive outcomes for Malaysians.

3.2 Malaysia MADANI: The Vision

At the heart of Malaysia MADANI lies the unwavering commitment to good governance, a cornerstone for a civilised, skilled, and inclusive society. With the six pillars, it is a vision that represents an aspirational future for Malaysia, a society that embodies the values of sustainability, prosperity, innovation, respect, trust, and compassion. It is a guiding principle that aims to transform Malaysia into a nation that is not only economically and technologically advanced but also deeply rooted in ethical values and social harmony. The

Malaysian Public Sector, as the custodian of the nation's resources and the provider of essential services, has a responsibility in emulating these values and translate them into tangible benefits for all Malaysians. They are essential in promoting positive change, exemplifying good governance, and ensuring Malaysia has a better future. The public sector can make Malaysia MADANI a reality by implementing transparent procurement procedures, citizen-centric services, technology adoption, data-driven decision-making, and an integrity-driven culture.

3.3 The G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service: The Driving Force

The G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service, located at the intersection of the three circles, embodies the driving force behind achieving Malaysia MADANI through good governance. With its commitment to excellence in public administration, the G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service ensures that the government delivers efficient, effective, and people-centric services. The journey towards Malaysia MADANI requires a collective effort, with the public sector as one of the main actors. Through the adoption of G.R.E.A.T. principles, the public sector can transform itself into a catalyst for positive change, driving Malaysia's progress towards a MADANI society. By embracing the principles of G.R.E.A.T., the Malaysian Public Sector can:

- Uphold good governance practices by ensuring transparency, accountability, and responsiveness in decision-making processes.
- Empathize with the needs of the people by understanding their concerns and aspirations, and tailoring policies and services accordingly.
- Hold themselves accountable for their actions and decisions, ensuring that they deliver on their promises to the public.
- Demonstrate tenacity of purpose in overcoming challenges and pursuing long-term goals for the betterment of society.

Briefly, this Euler diagram effectively captures the interconnectedness of good governance, Malaysia MADANI, and the G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service, highlighting their role in shaping a prosperous and harmonious nation. The overlapping areas in the diagram represent the synergistic relationship between these concepts, emphasizing their mutual support and the shared goal of societal progress.

4. IMPLEMENTATIONS OF G.R.E.A.T. IN MALAYSIAN PUBLIC SECTOR

Malaysian Public Sector is a very important part of the nation's economy. It is a place where civil servants are obliged to work together to make Malaysia a better place. This is because civil service is responsive to the needs of their citizens, and that it is a place where one can make their country a better place. Many governments throughout the world are taking a proactive stance in response to the issue to overcome time constraints and maintain the national development programme on track. The civil service, as a professional entity and the primary state instrument for managing good governance and growth, cannot afford to disregard developments and difficulties. The civil service must now rise to the occasion, which necessitates a thorough review of the situation, institutions, and business processes.

Public sectors worldwide encountered formidable challenges during the COVID-19 era, and Malaysia was no exception. Despite these unprecedented circumstances, Malaysia emerges resilient, overcoming these challenges through unwavering efforts. Now, in the post-pandemic era and the years ahead, Malaysia faces a new set of challenges, including a changing workforce, rapid digitalization, and the need for heightened responsiveness to citizen needs. To address these challenges, the Malaysian government has embarked on several initiatives under the G.R.E.A.T framework to accomplish more with less in order to satisfy citizens' growing needs and remove roadblocks to the growth of the private sector. These initiatives include:

4.1 G-Good Governance

The Good Governance element in the G.R.E.A.T framework, is a transitioning to a new public governance, whereby collaboration is a key component. Collaboration involves more than one party within the public sector or within and beyond the public sector working together in the areas of policy development, service design, or service delivery. In this context, dismantling silo mentalities and fostering collaborative efforts with all stakeholders are paramount to delivering superior public services. Collaborative governance emphasises a collective 'US' rather than an individualistic 'me and you' approach. To further enhance public trust and the overall effectiveness of public service delivery, continued efforts must be made to strengthen institutions, promote transparency, and actively engage citizens in the policymaking process.

4.2 R-Responsible

The RESPONSIBLE element shows that in today's fast-paced and ever-changing world, adapting coaching can be a valuable tool for helping organisations to stay ahead of the competition and achieve their goals. Coaching can be used in any type of organisation, at any level, and for any purpose. If one is looking for a way to improve the organization in giving seamless services, coaching is a great place to start.

4.3 E-Empathy

The success of a country depends upon its human capital and not just on the richness of its natural resources or the size of its population. Public service delivery is basically influenced by the capability, involvement, and ability of its human resource. Bearing this in mind, the Malaysian Public Service Department (MPSD) strives to achieve several objectives. MPSD rationalise the size of public service through systematic human resource planning. A positive idea for talent development is to produce competent human capital through dynamic training programmes and sponsorship programmes. Nurturing an environment that prioritises employee development and advancement can be achieved by cultivating an ecosystem rich in training, mentoring, and networking opportunities. Additionally, fostering a culture of acknowledgment and gratitude can instil a sense of belonging and community among employees.

4.4 A- Accountability

Public sector employees have the ability to make a genuine impact in the lives of others, which can be an extremely rewarding endeavour. To complete this, rebranding public

sectors to make real differences is required. This is because more young people are looking for jobs that have a good impact on the planet. As a result, public sectors must be more accountable in generating opportunities that allow people to work on critical issues such as climate change, poverty, and social justice.

4.5 T- Tenacity of Purpose

The last aspect is TENACITY OF PURPOSE, in which MPSD believes that by persevering in the face of enormous hurdles, the Government would be able to adopt and use digital technologies and data to modernise the public sector and become more citizen-centric in its ways. Businesses and governments must accelerate the adoption of digital technologies in order to remain competitive. This will include deciding which areas should be digitalised, prioritising technology solutions, and strengthening data privacy and cyber-security rules. For example, the MPSD, through the National Institute of Public Administration (INTAN), is spearheading a number of programmes and initiatives aimed at ensuring that 100% of Malaysian Civil Servants are digitally literate by 2025. The digital transition in Malaysia represents efficiency, efficacy, and transparency.

5. DISCUSSIONS

The G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service implementation in Malaysia resulted in many positive outcomes, including increased productivity, efficiency, and efficacy. Furthermore, it has fostered a more transparent, accountable, and responsive public sector, thereby bolstering public trust and confidence in the government. Enhanced service delivery and responsiveness to citizen needs had been realised through a more competent and applicable public sector, fueled by streamlined processes, reduced bureaucracy, and a focus on innovation. A culture of innovation permeated the public sector by promoting ethical conduct and accountability among public servants. This spurred interest from other nations to invest in Malaysia and produced excellent results in cutting superfluous public expenditures.

Referencing the prime minister's quote that "the paradigm must be shifted along with the welfare of the masses and uphold democratic accountability whereby one must be responsible for the way they act despite the freedom they have to do so" is a fundamental reminder for Malaysian Civil Service to be more people centric. As a result, online service platforms, systems for public feedback, and other efforts have been put into place with the goal of enhancing citizens' interactions with the government in general. In essence, the G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service has improved the quality of the workforce overall and given the Malaysian Public Sector access to a more rewarding, professional, and merit-based public service.

6. CONCLUSION

Poor life expectancy is a genuine problem for people who do not have adequate governance, economic and social security. It is apparent that those who lack socioeconomic security will be less able to carry on their culture than those who live in better-off locations. Because of inadequate public sector governance, they are likely to be physically and cognitively impoverished. They are also likely to be underdeveloped as a result of the government's failure to provide an enabling socioeconomic environment and security of life

and property. Lack of good governance has a negative impact on society's regeneration because culture and traditions are not consistently transferred to newer generations; systematic death of persons who would have passed on culture and custom leads to cultural extinction, and good governance as a value becomes virtually unknown in a society. Having said that, good governance is not merely a set of abstract ideals; it is a tangible force that transforms societies, it is a way of life that permeates every aspect of the public sector. It lays the groundwork for sustainable development, creating a society that embodies the values of Malaysia MADANI, a framework for collective action, and a shared aspiration that unites Malaysians from all walks of life. The G.R.E.A.T. Civil Service, guided by the principles of good governance, plays a pivotal role in realizing the MADANI vision.

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REFERENCES

1. PricewaterhouseCoopers. (2017, July 2). Government and Public Sector. PwC. <https://www.pwc.com/my/en/industry/government-public-sector.html>
2. Malapi-Nelson, Alcibiades (2017). "Cybernetics: The Book, the Club, and the Decline". *The Nature of the Machine and the Collapse of Cybernetics: A Transhumanist Lesson for Emerging Technologies*. Palgrave Studies in the Future of Humanity and its Successors. Cham (Zug): Springer. p. 48. Retrieved 26 August 2020. Plato used the term κυβερνητική in the *Georgias*, the *Laws* and the *Republic*, in order to refer to the 'art of navigation' (or proper steering) of a community. Plato was referring to the political art of governance.
3. Plattner, M. F. (2013). Reflections on "Governance". *J. Democracy*, 24, 17.
4. The World Bank. (1992) Governance and Development; World Bank Group.
5. UNDP. (1997, January). Governance for sustainable human development. New York; UNDP.
6. Policy Brief: What is good governance? (2009) United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific. (n.d.). <https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/good-governance.pdf>
7. World Bank. (1994). Governance: The World Bank's experience. The World Bank.
8. Chartered Institute of Public Finance and Accountancy, & International Federation of Accountants. (2014, July). International Framework: Good Governance In The Public Sector Executive Summary.
9. Othman Alkaff, S. H., & Jani, M. H. (2023). Malaysia Madani and the Muslim world: Anwar Ibrahim's Soft Power Strategy. – *The Diplomat*. <https://thediplomat.com/2023/07/malaysia-MADANI-and-the-muslim-world-anwar-ibrahims-soft-power-strategy/>

10. Abdul Rahman, N. A., & Abdul Karim, S. A. (2023). - The Malaysia Madani Framework: How Other Countries View The Framework. BERNAMA Thoughts. <https://www.bernama.com/en/thoughts/news.php?id=2218766>
11. MAMPU. (n.d.). Teks Ucaptama Yang Berbahagia Tan Sri Dato' Seri Mohd Zuki ... - mampu. <https://www.mampu.gov.my/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Teks-Ucapan-KSN-Majlis-Pelancaran-Buku-Modul-dan-Forum-GREAT-Civil-Service-20062023.pdf>